

The Attitudes of Sixth Preparatory Grade Students in Iraq towards Distance Arabic Language Education during the Coronavirus Crisis

Abed M. Al-Amery

Article Info

Article History

Received:
February 18, 2024

Accepted:
May 21, 2024

Keywords :

Attitudes, Coronavirus
Crisis, Iraq, Distance
Education, Sixth
Preparatory Grade
Students

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.11237083

Abstract

The present study aimed to explore the attitudes of sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq towards distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis. To have the study's goal met, the researcher adopted a descriptive analytical approach. He developed a questionnaire. He selected a random sample consisting from 180 female and male sixth preparatory grade students from 9 schools in Baghdad, Iraq. Questionnaire forms were distributed to the selected students. 172 forms were retrieved and deemed valid for analysis. SPSS software was used for analyzing data. It was found that the attitudes of sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq towards distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis are positive. It was found that distance Arabic language education improves students' reading, writing, listening and speaking skill and expands students' knowledge on Arabic language grammar. However, respondents find it difficult to keep themselves motivated while receiving distance Arabic language education.

Introduction

The demand for education has been increasing worldwide. Therefore, to meet such demand, the term (distance education) emerged. In distance education, the student and his/her instructor are spatially separated from each other. In simple words, in such education, the student shall not have a face to face contact with his/her instructor. Such education provides students in schools and universities with many choices in terms of choosing their instructors and the time, method and place of learning. It ensures that all citizens enjoy their right to education (Sadeghi, 2019). The number of the ones enrolled in distance education programs has been increasing worldwide due to social, economic and technological developments. Distance education changed the learning behaviors of students (Kadish, 2019). Some people believe that the expression (distance education) has emerged recently. However, that's incorrect! This expression emerged during the early 1700s in America and Great Britain. During the latter period of time, course materials, assignments, notes, and feedback were delivered to students through using the postal service. Later on, during the beginning of the twentieth century, mass communication (e.g. television and radio) were used for the delivery of distance education to students. After that, during the period (1980 -1990), pre-recorded videos and cassette recordings were employed for the delivery of distance education. Later on, since the 1990s, internet and computers have been employed for the delivery of distance education. That is because computers and internet became less expensive and more accessible (Harper et al., 2004). Distance education has several advantages. For instance, it can meet the educational needs of various types of learners, such as: visual and auditory learners. In addition, it enables students to overcome the limitations that are hindering them from meeting their educational needs. To illustrate more, it can meet the educational needs of the girls whose parents don't allow them to leave their home due to certain cultural beliefs that are dominant in their communities. It can meet the educational needs of the students who live in remote places that are far from the desired educational institutions. It can meet the educational needs of the students who aren't capable to pay the accommodation and travel costs that are associated with travelling to enroll in a specific educational institution. It can meet the educational needs of the students who have a physical disability that hinders them from leaving home to get education (Pant, 2014).

Although there are numerous benefits for distance education, several challenges are associated with it. For instance, there are technical problems faced by students when using the learning management system. The questions in the exams may not be based on the academic material that was given earlier to the students (Gok, 2015). Some students may not receive feedback on the submitted homework (Akhter and Akbar, 2015). During the year 2020, the world suffered from the Coronavirus crisis. Therefore, Iraq went into a lockdown. The Iraqi schools and universities were closed temporarily during this crisis. Therefore, university and school students were provided with distance education during this crisis. Taking this step indicates that the Iraqi government is

keen on providing university and school students with education in order to foster national development. In the light of that, the researcher of the present study aimed to explore the effectiveness of distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis from the perspective of sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq. It's necessary to explore that because Arabic language is the language of the Holy Quran. It's necessary to explore that because Arabic language is one of the most important languages in the world. The present study aimed to explore the attitudes of sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq towards distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis and to identify the challenges associated with distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis from the perspective of the sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq. The present study aimed to answer those questions: what are the attitudes of sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq towards distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis. And what are the challenges associated with distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis from the perspective of the sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq.

Significance of the Study

The present study provides decision makers the Iraqi Ministry of Education with important information that can improve the quality of the school distance education provided to students when experiencing a crisis. The present study provides policy makers in Iraq with knowledge about the challenges associated with distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis. Such knowledge shall enable those policy makers to make policies that address such challenges. As far as the researcher knows, this is the first study that aimed to explore the effectiveness of distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis from the perspective of sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq. Thus, it contributes to enriching the relevant literature

Limits and Limitations

- Temporal limits: The present study was conducted during the second semester of the academic year (2019/2020).
- Spatial limits: This study was conducted in Baghdad, Iraq.
- Human limits: This study selected a sample consisting from several sixth preparatory grade students in Baghdad, Iraq who were received Arabic language distance education during the Coronavirus crisis

The results of the present study can't be generalized to all the school students in Iraq. That is because students differ from each other in terms of ICT skills and interest in Arabic language. Such skills and interest shall affect students' attitudes towards Arabic language distance education.

Definition of Terms

Theoretical definitions

Attitude: It refers to a psychological tendency that represents the degree to which someone disfavors or favors a particular something (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993: 1). It refers to one's negative or positive feelings about doing a specific behavior (Fishbein and Ajzen 1975, p. 216).

Distance education: In distance education, the student and his/her instructor are spatially separated from each other. In simple words, in distance education, the student shall not have a face to face contact with his/her instructor (Sadeghi, 2019)

Operational definitions

- **Attitude:** It refers to the attitude of the sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq towards distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis.
- **Distance education:** It refers to the distance Arabic language education that is delivered for the sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq during the Coronavirus crisis.

Theoretical literature

Advantages of distance education

Students can immediately see the changes made to the academic material. In such programs, teachers have a better capability to identify the students' academic needs and assess students' amount knowledge on a specific subject. They are more capable to assign duties and tasks to each student based on his/her own skills and academic achievement level. They can update the academic material easily (Ally, 2004).

Distance education is characterized by three characteristics; convenience, flexibility and adaptability. These characteristics attract people to join distance education programs (Holmberg, 2005). In distance education programs, students can learn at any time. Thus, they may ask the teacher questions at any time. They can inform the teacher about any problem they face at any time. In such programs, there shall be less embarrassment associated with asking the teacher questions. That is because the student can't send the question to the teacher through the email. Such programs promote awareness among students about the advantages of using the internet. They promote a lifelong learning approach. That's because the web serves as an effective and easy educational method which is constantly provided with information (TERZİ, and ÇELİK, 2005).

Distance education promotes learner autonomy, and deep understanding for information. It enables students to learn at their own pace, and spend less time attempting to understand the required information (Wang, 2014). Distance education programs are characterized with flexibility. For instance, the student enrolled in such programs may learn at any time he/she wants. He/she can learn from any place he/she is located at. It is easy for students in these programs to access the academic material because it's uploaded to the web. Thus, the material may be accessed from any place and at any time. Furthermore, the fees of distance education programs are lower than the fees of conventional education programs. Thus, students can save money through enrolling in distance education programs (Oliveira et al., 2018).

Through distance education, the managements of educational facilities shall not have to search for physical space for having classes at. That's because the classes shall become virtual classes. In other words, the managements of educational facilities won't have to search for buildings to rent. Thus, they shall not have to get a business license for renting another building. They won't have to make any costly change to their buildings. That shall enable educational facilities to save costs. It shall enable the managements of educational facilities to register a great number of students without recruiting a great number of teachers. That is because the teachers in distance education programs may have the lesson record and sent to a great number of students in different classes (Oliveira et al., 2018).

Distance education offers students the opportunity to plan the way they want to learn. It offers students the opportunity to choose the time of studying. It offers university students the opportunity to work and study during the same period of time (Fojtík, 2018). It offers students many references that fit with their preferences and needs. It offers students equal opportunities to learn. It enables students to identify different opinions. That's because a distance education program may include students from various places of the world who shall interact with each other. Students in distance education programs are engaged in the teaching-learning process more than students in face-to-face educational programs. In addition, the outcomes of distance education programs are better than the outcomes of face-to-face educational programs (Kadish, 2019).

The challenges associated with distance education

There are many challenges associated with distance education. For instance, the students provided with distance education may consider their learning experiences depressing. That's because those students learn alone without having any one around them while learning (Hara and Kling, 2000). The students who take online exams at their home can't be monitored. Thus, the teacher can't ensure that the student himself/herself took the online exam (Kim and Shih, 2003). Some distance education programs, the online academic material that is sent to the students can't meet their academic needs.

Some distance education programs, the online academic material doesn't take into consideration the individual differences existing between students. Some distance education programs, the online academic material may be lacking a multimedia-based content. Furthermore, the students receiving distance education may doubt their learning capabilities. That is because there isn't any teacher around them to encourage and reward them (Attri, 2012). The student's learning process may be disrupted due to having an interaction with a family member in the room.

In such programs, the students may not be provided with feedback for their assignments and works. That shall oblige those students to assess their assignments and works by themselves. Furthermore, in such programs, there shall not be a sufficient communication between the students and their instructor. In fact, many weeks or days may pass without having a communication between the student and his/her instructor. However, the student may be having poor capabilities in assessing herself/himself. That shall have a negative impact on the quality of the education provided to the student. Such insufficient communication between the instructor and the students can be attributed to the difficulty faced by the instructor in replying fast to the numerous messages that he/she receives from students (Attri, 2012).

The students who receive distance education may suffer from having inadequate online services or online services of poor quality. Such services may include admission and library services. The aforementioned students may experience problems in accessing the digital library of the facility. They may experience problems in

contacting the administrative and academic staff (Attri, 2012). There are psychological problems facing the students who are provided with distance education. For instance, it's suggested that distance education negatively affects students' self-confidence. It's suggested that such education promotes frustration among students. That is because those students experience social isolation. In some programs, those students aren't provided with training about the way of using ICTs. That shall hinder those students from learning effectively. In addition, some students aren't literate. That shall hinder them from receiving distance education because they won't be capable to use the learning management system, nor read the academic material uploaded to the web. Some teachers in distance education programs have poor ICT skills which hinder students from learning as required (Attri, 2012). Students' satisfaction and enjoyment with the distance educational program are influenced by their skills in using ICTs. Thus, the students with poor ICT skills may not feel satisfied with such programs nor enjoy enrolling in them.

In addition, in distance educational programs, students are not provided with learning experiences that are multisensory. That shall negatively influence the learning outcomes. Students in distance educational programs may lose interest in learning due to having a delay in replies. In such programs, the opportunities to have conversations between students are scarce (Wang, 2014). Delivering distance education requires making much preparation by the teachers. It requires providing the users of the learning management system with much online security which is something challenging. In addition, some teachers may think that they can use the same teaching methods used in conventional education programs. However, that's not true. Doing that shall negatively affect the quality of the provided education (Fojtík, 2018). In distance education programs, it would be difficult for students to keep themselves self-motivated. That is because the teacher isn't always there to motivate students (Sadeghi, 2019).

Empirical literature

Sai et al. (2013) aimed to identify the challenges which are faced by the university students in an English language online course in Malaysia. The sample consists from 512 students. A five point Likert questionnaire was used for having the required data collected. It was found that those students face technical problems when downloading the academic material uploaded the web. In addition, the students weren't provided with training for improving their communication skills. The online exercises / information aren't adequate for improving the students' language proficiency. Furthermore, many students didn't receive feedback which hindered them from identifying their mistakes. The respondents faced difficulty in contacting their instructors (Sai et al., 2013).

Rhema and Miliszewska (2014) aimed to explore the undergraduates' attitudes in Libya towards e-learning. A questionnaire was used for collecting data. The sample consists from 348 undergraduates who were selected from Libyan universities. The SPSS program was used for analyzing data. It was found that ICT makes learning enjoyable and expands students' knowledge. ICT increase the quality of the teaching-learning process and students' satisfaction with the latter process. There is a significant positive relationship between students' access to ICT and skills in using ICT.

Ekmekçi (2014) aimed to explore the attitudes of freshmen towards online learning in English language course during the academic year 2013-2014. A questionnaire was used. The sample consists from 72 freshmen in Turkey. For analyzing data, SPSS program was used. It was found that the respondents are satisfied with learning English language online in terms of the website format, reading, content and grammar. However, the respondents aren't satisfied in terms of the writing, speaking and listening sections of the course. The students' responsibilities and assignments in the online course aren't clear. Some students weren't provided with feedback. Some students aren't satisfied with the grading system and assessment methods used in the course. The respondents enjoyed the course due to its flexibility in terms of time and place (Ekmekçi, 2014).

Raba' (2016) aimed to explore the attitude of students at Al- Quds Open University towards distance education. A random sample was selected. It consists from 92 female and male students. A thirty-item questionnaire was used. The latter researcher calculated means and percentages and conducted the t-test and ANOVA analysis. It was found that distance education is motivational and promotes learner autonomy. Such education attracts students' attention due to the use of ICTs. It makes students open minded. It expands students' knowledge and develops their skills. Students value distance education because it enables them to choose the way and time of studying. They value distance education because it enables them to overcome financial and spatial barriers. Through distance education, students can perform self-assessment due to having pre-assigned objectives (Raba', 2016).

Ozturk (2016) aimed to explore the attitudes of the students in the vocational schools of Dokuz Eylul University towards distance education. The latter university is located in Izmir, Turkey. They used a questionnaire for collecting data. The sample consists from 128 female and male students. The SPSS program was used. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted. An independent-samples t-test was conducted. It was found that the respondents have negative attitudes towards distance education. It was found that there isn't any statistically

significant difference between the respondents' attitudes which can be attributed to age. It was found that male respondents have more positive attitudes than female respondents towards distance education (Ozturk, 2016). Gossenheimer et al. (2017) aimed to explore the effectiveness of distance education in raising the academic achievement of the students majoring in pharmacy. An experimental approach was adopted. The sample consists from 82 students who were divided into control and experimental groups. Pre-test and post-test were administered. It was found that distance education is more effective than face-to-face education in raising the academic achievement of the students majoring in pharmacy (Gossenheimer et al., 2017).

Method

Methods of Data Collection

The researcher adopted a descriptive analytical approach. The researcher collected data through distributing questionnaire forms to the sampled students. He also reviewed several books, and studies (including theoretical and empirical studies).

Sample and Population

The population consists from all the sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq who received distance education during the Coronavirus crisis. The researcher employed the random sampling method. He selected 180 female and male sixth preparatory grade students from 9 schools. To be specific, 20 sixth preparatory grade students were selected from each school. Out of those nine schools, five schools are for boys and four schools are for girls. Out of those nine schools, five schools are public schools, three schools are private schools, and one school is an evening school. All the selected schools are located in Baghdad, Iraq. Questionnaire forms were distributed to the selected students. To be specific, they were distributed online to 100 male students and 80 female students. However, 172 forms were retrieved and deemed valid for statistical analysis. Table (1) presents the distribution of the sample in accordance with gender

Table 1. Distribution of the sample in accordance with gender

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	95	55.23
	Female	77	44.76

N=172

Based on table (1), 55.23% of the respondents are males and 44.76% of the respondents are females.

Instrument

Based on the relevant studies and books, the researcher developed a questionnaire that consists from three parts. The first part collects data about gender. It suggests that data shall remain confidential. It identifies the title and goals of the research. The second part collects data about the respondents' attitudes towards distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis. It consists from 13 items. It was developed based on the works of the following researchers: Ekmekçi (2014), Sadeghi (2019), Wang (2014), Raba' (2016) and Oliveira et al. (2018). The third part collects data about the challenges associated with distance education in Iraq during the Coronavirus crisis. It consists from seven items. It was developed based on the works of the following researchers: Gok (2015), Attri (2012) Akhter and Akbar (2015) and Sai et al. (2013). The questionnaire was distributed in Arabic language. It was translated into English language to be presented in this study.

Validity of the Instrument

To measure the questionnaire's validity, two experts were asked to assess the initial version of the questionnaire in terms of clarity, language and relevancy to the study's questions. The questionnaire was passed to them in Arabic language. Those experts are faculty members working in Iraqi universities. They hold a PhD degree in educational sciences and have much experience. They suggested that the questionnaire is clear, free from language mistakes and relevant to the study's questions. One of the experts recommended re-drafting two statements. Those items were re-drafted.

Reliability of the Instrument

To measure the questionnaire's reliability, the Cronbach alpha coefficient value is calculated. It's 0.871. This value indicates that the questionnaire is reliable and provides one with reliable results.

Methods and Criteria for Data analysis

The researcher used descriptive statistics and the SPSS software. The following methods were used to analyze data

- Standard deviations and means are calculated to answer the study's questions
- Percentages and frequencies are calculated to identify the characteristics of the sample.
- The cronbach alpha coefficient value is calculated to measure the reliability of the questionnaire

For classifying means, specific criteria were adopted by the researcher. These criteria are presented through the table shown below.

Table 2. The criteria employed to classify means

Range	Level	Attitude
2.33 or less	Low	Negative attitude
2.34-3.66	Moderate	Neutral attitude
3.67 or more	High	Positive attitude

*Source: Aljbour (2020)

The five point Likert scale involves 5 rating categories. The latter categories are shown through the table below

Table 3. The categories and scores of the five point Likert scale

Category	Score
Strongly agree	5
Agree	4
Neutral	3
Disagree	2
Strongly disagree	1

*Source: Aljbour (2020)

Results and Discussion

Discussion and Results related to the First Question

Table (4) presents the respondents' attitudes towards distance Arabic language education in Iraq during the Coronavirus crisis.

Table 4. The respondents' attitudes towards distance Arabic language education in Iraq during the Coronavirus crisis

No.	Statement	Mean	Std.	Level	Attitude
1.	Distance Arabic language education improves my Arabic language reading skills	4.92	0.31	High	Positive
2.	Distance Arabic language education improves my Arabic language writing skills	4.86	0.29	High	Positive
3.	Distance Arabic language education improves my Arabic language listening skills	4.81	0.68	High	Positive
4.	Distance Arabic language education improves my Arabic language speaking skills	4.69	0.45	High	Positive
5.	Distance Arabic language education expands my knowledge on Arabic language grammar	4.75	0.17	High	Positive
6.	It's easy to keep myself motivated while receiving distance Arabic language education	2.24	0.50	Low	Negative
7.	I am satisfied with my experience in receiving distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus	4.61	0.67	High	Positive
8.	Distance Arabic language education promotes deep understanding for information.	4.82	0.23	High	Positive
9.	Distance Arabic language education enables me to learn at my own pace	4.49	0.34	High	Positive

10.	There are many opportunities to have conversations between students while receiving distance Arabic language education	2.12	0.75	Low	Negative
11.	In distance Arabic language education, I can perform self-assessment	2.32	0.53	Low	Negative
12.	Distance Arabic language education is flexible	4.76	0.59	High	Positive
13.	Distance Arabic language education promotes learner autonomy	4.54	0.17	High	Positive
	Total	4.14	0.43	High	Positive

Based on table (4), respondents' attitudes towards distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis are positive. That's because the overall mean is 4.14 which is high. The overall standard deviation is 0.43. It was found that the distance Arabic language education improves students' Arabic language reading skills because the mean of statement 1 is 4.92. The latter result is consistent with the result concluded by Ekmekçi (2014). It was found that the distance Arabic language education improves students' Arabic language writing, listening and speaking skills. That's because the mean of statement 2, 3 and 4 are 4.86, 4.81, and 4.69 respectively. The latter result is inconsistent with the result concluded by Ekmekçi (2014). It may be attributed to the fact that distance education, offers students, many opportunities to contact experts in Arabic language. Contacting such experts shall offer students., many opportunities to practice the language which shall lead to improving their language skills. It was found that the distance Arabic language education expands students' knowledge on Arabic language grammar. That's because the mean of statement 5 is 4.75. The latter result is consistent with the result concluded by Ekmekçi (2014). It may be attributed to the fact that distance education, offers students, opportunities to access digital libraries which include many books on grammar. It was found that it's difficult for students to keep themselves motivated while receiving distance Arabic language education. That's because the mean of statement 6 is 2.24. The latter result is consistent with what is suggested by Sadeghi (2019). It may be attributed to the fact that the teachers in distance education programs aren't always there to motivate the students and reward them for showing a good achievement. It was found that the respondents are satisfied with their experience in receiving distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus. That's because the mean of statement 7 is 4.61. It was found that distance Arabic language education promotes a deep understanding of information. That's because the mean of statement 8 is 4.82. The latter result is consistent with what is suggested by Wang (2014). It was found that distance Arabic language education enables students to learn at their own pace. That's because the mean of statement 9 is 4.49. The latter result is consistent with what is suggested by Wang (2014). It may be attributed to the fact that students can re-watch the recorded video till they master the required skill or understand the required information. It was found that distance Arabic language education doesn't offer students, many opportunities to have conversations with each other. That is because the mean of statement 10 is 2.12. The latter result is consistent with what is suggested by Wang (2014). It was found that the students receiving distance Arabic language education can't perform self-assessment. That's because the mean of statement 11 is 2.32. The latter result is inconsistent with the result concluded by Raba' (2016). It may be attributed to the fact that the effective assessment is the one conducted by an expert or an instructor rather than the student himself/herself. That's because the student can't realize the gaps in his/her own knowledge and skills by himself/herself. It was found that distance Arabic language education is flexible because the mean of statement 12 is 4.76. The latter result is consistent with what is suggested by Oliveira et al. (2018). It may be attributed to the fact that those students can access the online material at any time and place. Thus, students can learn, though there are temporal, and spatial limitations. It was found that distance Arabic language education promotes learner autonomy because the mean of statement 13 is 4.54. The latter result is consistent with the result concluded by Raba' (2016). It may be attributed to the fact that distance Arabic language education is based on the self-study approach. Thus, students should rely on themselves for collecting and analyzing information and reaching knowledge.

Discussion and Results related to the Second Question

Table (5) presents the challenges associated with distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis from the perspective of the sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq.

Table 5. The challenges associated with distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis from the perspective of the sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq

No.	Statement	Mean	Std.	Level	Attitude
1.	The questions in the Arabic language online exams are based on the academic material given to me	1.75	0.34	Low	Negative

		earlier			
2.	There are difficulties in contacting the Arabic language teacher while receiving distance Arabic language education	4.83	0.67	High	Positive
3.	While receiving distance Arabic language education, I am not always provided with feedback from the Arabic language teachers on the assignments I submit	4.92	0.21	High	Positive
4.	The Arabic language teacher's teaching methods don't fit with the nature of distance education	4.53	0.40	High	Positive
5.	The online material in the Arabic language course doesn't take into consideration the individual differences between students	4.47	0.57	High	Positive
6.	I faced technical problems in using the learning management system while receiving distance Arabic language education	4.60	0.33	High	Positive
7.	The Arabic language teacher has poor ICT skills that negatively affects my online learning experience	4.37	0.24	High	Positive
Total		4.21	0.39	High	Positive

Based on table (5), the severity of the challenges associated with distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis is high. That is because the overall mean is 4.21. It was found that the questions in the Arabic language online exams are not based on the academic material that was given to the students earlier. That's because the mean of statement 1 is 1.75. The latter result is inconsistent with the result concluded by Gok (2015).

It was found that there are difficulties in contacting the Arabic language teachers while receiving distance Arabic language education because the mean of statement 2 is 4.83. The latter result is consistent with what is suggested by Attri (2012). It was found that students aren't always provided with feedback from the Arabic language teachers on the assignments they submit. That's because the mean of statement 3 is 4.92. The latter result is consistent with the result concluded by Akhter and Akbar (2015).

It was found that the Arabic language teachers' teaching methods don't fit with the nature of distance education because the mean of statement 4 is 4.53. That indicates that Arabic language teachers in Iraq must be provided with more training courses about teaching methods. It was found that the online material in the Arabic language course doesn't take into consideration the individual differences between students because the mean of statement 5 is 4.47. The latter result is consistent with what is suggested by Attri (2012).

It was found that the respondents faced technical problems in using the learning management system while receiving distance Arabic language education, because the mean of statement 6 is 4.60. The latter result is consistent with the result concluded by Sai et al. (2013). It was found that Arabic language teachers in Iraq have poor ICT skills that negatively affects students' learning experience, because the mean of statement 7 is 4.37. The latter result is consistent with what is suggested by Attri (2012). That means that Arabic language teachers in Iraq must be provided with more training courses about the use of ICTs.

Conclusion

It was found that the attitudes of sixth preparatory grade students in Iraq towards distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis are positive. It was found that there are many advantages for distance Arabic language education. For instance, distance Arabic language education improves students' reading, writing, listening and speaking skills. It expands students' knowledge on Arabic language grammar. It promotes deep understanding for information, and enables students to learn at their own pace. In the light of these results, the researcher of the present study believes that language centers should offer online language programs. That is need because some people don't have much free time. He also believes that Iraqi public and private schools must offer online programs. That is because some students face difficulties in going to schools. Such studies include: disabled students and the students living in remote areas. It was found that the severity of the challenges associated with distance Arabic language education during the Coronavirus crisis is high. It was found that there are difficulties in contacting the Arabic language teachers while receiving distance Arabic language education. That is because teachers shall not be available on the web 24 hours/ a day. Thus, the student may have to wait for several days till receiving the reply from his/her Arabic language teacher. It was found that students faced technical problems in using the learning management system while receiving distance Arabic

language education. That indicates that IT specialists must exert more effort to improve the learning management system. It means that more funds must be dedicated by the Iraqi Ministry of Education for improving the educational systems and websites used by school students.

Recommendations

In the light of the results, the researcher recommends

- Developing policies by the Iraqi Ministry of Education for addressing the challenges that faced the students who received distance education during the Coronavirus crisis.
- Adding online activities to school curricula in Iraq.
- Providing teachers in Iraq with training courses about the strategies used for delivering distance education

Acknowledgement

The researcher would like to thank the Ministry of Education in Iraq for exerting much effort.

References

- Akhter, N.; and Akbar, R. (2015). Problems of distance learners regarding assessment process in Pakistan. *Bulletin of Education and Research*. 37(2), 59-67
- Aljbour, H. (2020). The extent of practicing ethical leadership by public secondary school principals in Amman. *Journal of Education and Practice*. 11(15). 57-63, DOI: 10.7176/JEP/11-15-07
- Ally, M. (2004). Foundations of educational theory for online learning. In Anderson, T. & Elloumi, F. (Ed.). *The theory and practice of online learning* (pp. 15-44). Athabasca University Press.
- Attri, A. (2012). Distance education: problems and solutions. *International Journal of Behavioral Social and Movement Sciences*, 1(4). 42-58
- Eagly, A. and Chaiken, S. (1993). *The psychology of attitudes*, Belmont USA: Wadsworth.
- Ekmekçi, E. (2014). Distance-education in foreign language teaching: evaluations from the perspectives of freshman students, *International Educational Technology Conference*, September, 3rd-5th, 2014, Chicago, USA
- Fishbein, M. and Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief, attitude, intention, and behavior: An introduction to theory and research*. Reading, MA: Addison, Wesley.
- Fojtki, R. (2018). Problems of distance education. *International Journal of Information and Communication Technologies in Education (ICTE)*. 7(1), 14-23
- Gok, T. (2015). The evaluations of the college students' perceptions on distance education from the point of the technical and educational factors. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education-TOJDE*. 16(2), 84-93
- Gossenheimer, A.; Bem, T; Carneiro, M.; and Castro, M. (2017). The impact of distance education on academic performance in a pharmaceutical care course. *PLoS One*. 12(4).
- Hara, N., & Kling, R. (2000). Student distress in a web-based distance education course. *Information, Communication & Society*, 3(4), 557-579.
- Harper, K.; Chen, K.; & Yen, D. (2004). Distance learning, virtual classrooms, and teaching pedagogy in the Internet environment. *Technology in Society*, 26.585-598.
- Holmberg, B. (2005). *Theory and practice of distance education*. New York, USA, Routledge.
- Kadish, P. (2019). Distance education and online learning in Thailand's higher education. *Journal of Education and Practice*. 10(21).40-43
- Kim, W.; and Shih, T. (2003). Distance education: The status and challenges. *Journal of Object Technology*, 2(6). 35-43
- Oliveira, M.; Penedo, A.; Pereira, V. (2018). Distance education: advantages and disadvantages of the point of view of education and society. *Dialogia*, São Paulo, (29), p. 139-152. DOI: 10.5585/Dialogia.n29.7661
- Ozturk, K. (2016). Associate degree students' attitudes towards distance education at the vocational schools of Dokuz Eylul University. *Education Journal*. 5(1), 7-11. doi: 10.11648/j.edu.20160501.12
- Pant, A. (2014). Distance learning: history, problems and solutions. *Advances in Computer Science and Information Technology (ACSIT)*. 1(2). 65-70
- Raba', A. (2016). Students' attitude towards distance learning at Al-Quds Open University/ Tulkarem educational region. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 5(2), 1157-1164
- Rhema, A., & Miliszewska, I. (2014). Analysis of student attitudes towards e-learning: The case of engineering students in Libya. *Issues in Informing Science and Information Technology*, 11, 169-190. Retrieved from: <http://iisit.org/Vol11/IISITv11p169-190Rhema0471.pdf>
- Sadeghi, M. (2019). A shift from classroom to distance learning: advantages and limitations *International Journal of Research in English Education*. 4(1). P.80-88

- Sai, G.; Lin, A.; and Belaja, K. (2013). Challenges faced by distance learners to learn the English language at the school of distance education, UniversitiSains Malaysia. *Malaysian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(1), 43–53
- TERZİ, S.; and ÇELİK, A. (2005). Teacher-student interactions in distance learning. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology – TOJET*, 4(1), 54-56
- Wang, H. (2014). Challenges for distance education: a cultural analytic perspective on asynchronous online courses in Sweden. Published MA thesis. Lund University, Sweden

Author Information

Abed Al-Amery

The Institute of Fine Arts for Males and Females
Baghdad - Iraq
